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Effect of Audit Switching on Firms Value in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examines the effect of audit switching on firms value in Nigeria. The study is vital as it portrays the extent to which audit switching has influenced firm's value in Nigeria. In order to determine the relationship between audit switching and firms value, some key proxy variables were used in the study, namely Audit Switching (AS) while firm's value was proxy by Net Assets Per Share (NAPS). A hypothesis was formulated to guide the investigation and the statistical test of parameter estimates was conducted using OLS Model. The research design used is *ex-post facto* design and data for the study were obtained from the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) Factbook. The findings of the study show that AS has no significant effect on firms value in Nigeria This goes further to confirm that switching of audit firm by organizations has no significant contribution towards the firms value in Nigeria. Based on this, the study recommended that the importance of auditors switching in Nigerian firms cannot be over emphasized. Therefore firms should make sure that they seek the partnership of one of the big four (4) auditors if they want a quality audit report instead of switching from one audit firm to another.

Keywords: Audit switching, Firms' Value, Net Assets Per Share

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Audit involves carrying out procedures to gather evidence on the amounts and disclosures presented in the financial statements, with the goal of assessing the appropriateness of management's accounting estimates (KPMG, 2008). Audit quality is therefore a key factor in strengthening the credibility of financial statements for users of accounting information. The quality of an audit largely depends on the auditor's independence, which in turn is influenced by the auditor's familiarity with the client. However, when an auditor becomes too familiar with a client, it can compromise their independence (Imegi & Oladutire, 2018; Oghenekaro, Nkechi & Ekene, 2020). When auditor independence is impaired, the quality of audit suffers. Therefore, auditor rotation is a means of maintaining auditor's independence. Mandatory audit firm rotation is defined in the Sarbanes - Oxley (SOX) Act section 207 as the imposition of a limit on the period of years during which an accounting firm may be the auditor of record. The issue of audit tenure arises from concerns that long-term relationships between auditors and clients can lead auditors to become overly aligned with management, thereby compromising their independence (Gray & Manson, 2008, Ede, et al, 2025). To address this, it has been suggested that audits should be periodically rotated, offering key benefits such as: (i) ensuring an independent review of the prior auditor's work; (ii) promoting innovation in audit practices; and (iii) reducing the likelihood of auditor complacency (Gray & Manson, 2008). The concept of auditor switching has been debated for decades. As early as 1976, Senator Metcalf proposed auditor rotation as a safeguard against the risks of excessive familiarity. Audit firm switching extends the principle of audit partner rotation by mandating the replacement of the entire audit firm after a set number of years. Furthermore, the outgoing firm is typically restricted from re-engaging with the same client until after a designated cooling-off period.

Numerous studies (Arruñada & Paz-Ares, 1997; Healey & Kim, 2003; Brody & Moscove, 1998; Dopuch, King & Schwartz, 2001) have examined factors that may explain the practice of auditor switching, making it a subject of ongoing debate. Should companies regularly change their auditors, or is it better to allow auditors to develop long-term relationships with their clients?

Research findings on the impact of auditor switching on firm value are divided. Several studies (Healy & Kim, 2003; AICPA, 1992; Carcello & Nagy, 2004) view switching audit firms as a means to improve performance, arguing that over time, auditors' familiarity with clients diminishes the fresh perspective and critical approach they bring early in the engagement. This belief is reflected in the Sarbanes-Oxley Act of 2002, which mandates the rotation of lead audit partners every five years to ensure the audit is approached "with fresh and skeptical eyes." The underlying argument is that extended audit tenures can carry an opportunity cost by eroding auditor independence. In contrast, other scholars (Ghosh & Moon, 2005; DeFond & Francis, 2005; Oghenekaro & Ogheneovo, 2024) contend that longer auditor tenures enhance audit quality and firm value, as auditors need time to develop specialized knowledge of the client's business. According to this view, audit quality tends to be weaker in the initial years of an auditor-client relationship but improves over time as information asymmetry decreases (Azizkhani, Monroe & Shailer, 2006). Despite extensive research, there is still no clear consensus, especially in developed economies regarding the effect of auditor switching on firm performance and value, highlighting the need for further investigation. In the Nigerian audit environment, the issue of auditor switching and the dynamics of auditor-client relationships remain relatively underexplored, having attracted little analytical or empirical attention beyond anecdotal commentary. As a result, there is a significant gap in research and a lack of robust empirical evidence from Nigeria. Notably, no prior study has specifically focused on the construction and real estate sectors to assess the impact of auditor switching on firm value in the Nigerian context. This study, therefore, seeks to fill that gap by providing empirical evidence on whether auditor switching influences firm value in Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine the effect of audit switching on firms' value in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The research questions that are set to this paper include to:

What is the effect of Audit Switching on firms' value in Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis

In order to direct the direct flow of this study, the following hypothesis were formulated in line with objectives of the study

H₀₁: Audit Switching has no significant effect on firms' value in Nigeria.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

Audit Switching

The International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board (IAASB), under the International Federation of Accountants (IFAC), defines an audit as an independent examination and an expression of opinion on a business enterprise's financial statements, carried out by an appointed auditor in accordance with their appointment terms and in compliance with relevant legal and performance standards. The audit report represents the final product of this process, through which the auditor provides their opinion to the company's members on the fairness and accuracy of the financial statements. In Nigeria, the statutory framework for audits is provided by Section 359(1) of the Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA), 1990. Furthermore, Section 359(3) mandates that the auditor deliver a report to the members of the audit committee, which must be formally established by the client company. According to Ebimobowei and Oyadonghan (2011), encouraging auditor rotation policies can positively affect audit quality by introducing fresh perspectives and reinforcing public trust in the auditing function. On the contrary, Adeyemi and Okpala (2011) point out that changing auditors can sometimes threaten auditor independence, as long-term relationships between auditors and clients can lead to aligned interests, reducing the likelihood of objective, independent behavior. Barbadillo and Aguilar (2008) discovered an

inverse relationship between auditor switching and audit quality, suggesting that auditors tend to show greater dependence during the early years of a new engagement. Their research implies that shorter auditor tenures may result in less independent auditor behavior. High-quality auditor reporting is essential for enhancing the credibility of financial statements among stakeholders. However, such quality is only achievable if auditors maintain their independence. Without independence, auditors risk delivering biased opinions that favor the client. One significant factor that threatens auditor independence is the development of close, long-term relationships between auditors and their clients. Olowookere and Adebisi (2013) argued that auditor rotation helps prevent overly close auditor-client relationships and incentivizes firms to uphold high standards, as their work will eventually be scrutinized by successor auditors. Similarly, Dopuch, King, and Schwartz (2001) found that switching auditors reduces bias in audit reports. Lu and Sivaramakrishnan (2009) observed that auditor rotation reduces the likelihood of financial overstatements and increases conservative reporting practices. Catanach and Walker (2009) highlighted that auditor switching improves the quality of audit services, as firms seek to stand out by providing superior work. When the same auditor works with a client for extended periods, familiarity can lead to complacency, where the auditor anticipates the client's processes instead of rigorously reviewing them. This diminishes the quality and value of the audit. Therefore, auditor rotation helps limit the formation of close relationships that could compromise independence, ultimately improving audit quality and safeguarding the integrity of financial reporting.

2.1.2 Firms' Value

A firm's value signifies its capacity to generate economic wealth, serving as a critical indicator of its financial health and market standing. The primary objective in corporate decision-making be it investment or financing—is to maximize the firm's total market value, influenced by prevailing market conditions and security prices. Fama (1978) posited that in a perfect capital market, where investors and firms have equal access to capital, a firm's financing decisions do not affect its market value, rendering such decisions inconsequential to security holders. However, the assumption of equal access is often unrealistic, especially in emerging markets. Recent studies, such as Bui, Nguyen, and Pham (2023), have demonstrated that capital structure decisions can significantly impact firm value, indicating that financing choices are indeed consequential in real-world scenarios. Firm value, also known as enterprise value (EV), is a comprehensive measure reflecting the market value of a business. It encompasses the total value of all ownership interests and asset claims from both debt and equity holders. The standard formula for calculating EV is:
$$\text{Enterprise Value (EV)} = \text{Market Capitalization} + \text{Total Debt} + \text{Preferred Shares} + \text{Minority Interest} - \text{Cash and Cash Equivalents}.$$
 This metric provides a more holistic view of a company's worth compared to market capitalization alone, as it accounts for the company's capital structure and cash holdings. EV is particularly useful in valuation analyses, mergers and acquisitions, and comparing companies with different capital structures. In summary, while theoretical models suggest financing decisions may not affect firm value in perfect markets, empirical evidence indicates that in practice, these decisions can have significant implications. Enterprise value remains a vital tool for assessing a firm's overall market value, providing insights that extend beyond traditional equity measures.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The Lending Credibility Theory, developed by Hayes, Dassen, Schilder, and Wallage in 2005, posits that audited financial statements are used by management to strengthen stakeholders' trust in the company's stewardship. According to this theory, the primary role of auditing is to add credibility to the financial statements. By providing audited reports, management (acting as agents) aims to increase the principals' (owners or shareholders) confidence in how the business is being run and to reduce information asymmetry between them. Audited financial statements are viewed as containing elements that boost users' confidence in the figures and disclosures presented by management. The enhanced credibility is believed to provide tangible benefits to financial statement users, particularly by improving the quality of investment and decision-making, as decisions based on reliable, verified information are generally of higher quality.

This study is grounded in the Lending Credibility Theory, which is particularly relevant because it explains why managers may be motivated to switch to higher-quality audit firms. Company owners consistently seek the services of reputable, high-quality auditors to ensure more effective monitoring of management's activities and stewardship. This theory serves as the main theoretical foundation for the study, significantly shaping its research approach, guiding the formulation of hypotheses, and informing the choice of research methods and statistical techniques.

Empirical Review

Oghenekaro and Ogheneovo (2024) looked at determinants of audit switching in Nigerian healthcare firms. Using longitudinal data gathered from the firms' financial records over a range of 2010-2019, their study employed an *ex-post facto* research design. Using firm assets base, management changes, leverage financing, and audit fees as explanatory variables, while audit switching was used as dependent variable. A regression approach was used to analyse the gathered data. In order to determine whether the data used were normal and to look for multi-collinearity, some preliminary analysis were carried out using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and variance inflator analysis. The findings revealed that 68.69 percent of audit switches in Nigerian healthcare organisations are positively impacted by the independent variables that were chosen for the study. The particular result indicates that among Nigerian healthcare organisations that transfer auditors, the firm's asset base, a change in management, and leverage financing all have a favourable and significant. In Nigerian healthcare organisations, audit switching is positively but marginally influenced by audit fees and suggests that the main factors influencing audit switching among healthcare companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group are firm asset base, management changes, and leverage financing. While audit fees do influence audit switching, their influence is not as great.

Oghenekaro, Nkechi, and Ekene (2022) asset base, change in management and audit switching in Nigeria: empirical evidence *ex-post facto* research design was adopted and used longitudinal data collected from the financial reports of the firms for the various years. Assets base, and change in management as independent variables while audit switching was used as dependent variable. Data collected were analysed using regression analysis and some other preliminary analysis like descriptive statistics, correlation, and variance inflator analysis were carried out to ascertain the normality and check for the presence of multicollinearity. The finding reveals that assets base and change in management has positive and significant influence on audit switching among healthcare firms in Nigerian and suggests that to reduce the audit switching, shareholders should use consider the special skill requirement before engaging an auditor.

Between the 2015 and 2019 fiscal years, Ugwu (2020) explored the factors that influenced auditor changes among quoted companies in Nigeria. The study focused on three main variables: audit firm size, audit tenure, and audit fees. Using an *ex-post facto* research approach, the researcher analyzed secondary data from consumer goods firms through correlation analysis, binary logit and probit models, extreme value regression, and descriptive statistics. The results showed that while audit fees and audit firm size had a positive but statistically insignificant effect on auditor switching, audit tenure had a strong negative impact, indicating that longer relationships with auditors reduced the likelihood of a switch.

Between 2012 and 2015, Meryka and Evita (2017) explored the determinants of auditor switching among firms listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. The study investigated variables such as audit delay, client size, and changes in the audit committee, using binary logistic regression to analyze panel data from 156 purposively selected companies. The findings revealed that all examined factors had a significant influence on the decision to change auditors. Specifically, audit delay and audit committee changes had a positive but limited impact, while client size was found to negatively and significantly affect auditor switching.

In a 2016 study, Tan, Tze, Chong, and Adedeji examined the relationship between the financial performance of Malaysian listed companies, auditor switching, and corporate governance practices. Using panel data from 100 listed firms spanning 2009 to 2013, the researchers analyzed variables such as board

size, auditor switching, firm performance, board independence, and CEO duality. The study employed regression analysis and descriptive statistics for data evaluation. The findings indicated that CEO duality positively influenced auditor switching, while board independence had no significant effect on firm performance. The study provided valuable insights for policymakers, highlighting the role of auditors as assurance agents in strengthening the link between corporate governance and financial performance.

Kolawole and Godwin (2016) examined the key factors influencing auditor selection decisions among Nigerian listed industrial firms. The study utilized both primary and secondary sources of data, with purposive sampling used to select the participating companies. Primary data were obtained through structured questionnaires, while secondary data were drawn from the firms' annual financial statements. Data analysis was carried out using binary logistic regression and descriptive statistics. The results indicated that global reach and the existence of a long-standing relationship with the current auditor were the most influential factors affecting auditor change.

Johnson and Waidi (2013) on audit switching and audit quality in Nigerian deposit money banks used binary logit regression model and found that audit switching rule does not affect the audit quality.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The research design used is ex post facto design. It is a design that predicts the effect of one variable (explanatory variables) on the other variable (dependent variable) using already existed data that cannot be controlled or manipulated (Orife & Oghenekaro, 2024). This was used in the study in order to examine effect of audit switching on firms value in Nigeria with reference to all firms quoted under construction and real estate sector of NGX spanning form 2012-2020. The study used the entire firms quoted under construction and real estates. It includes; Roads Nig Plc, UPDC Nig Plc, Unuon Homes Plc, Smart Prod Plc, Julius Berger Plc, Arbico Plc, UACN Plc and Skye Shelter Plc.

Data for the study were obtained from the NGX Factbook and annual reports and accounts of the firms. The collected data was analyzed using OLS Model.

Operationalization and Measurement of Variables

The dependent variable in this study is liquidity and profitability and it were proxy using the variables as shown on the table below:

Table 1: Variable Measurements

S/N	VARIABLES	FORMULA	Apriori Expectations
	Dependent		
1	Firms Value	NAPS: Net Assets/Paid up Capital	Brockman (2015), Nahiba (2017)
	Independent		
2	Audit Switching	AS: measured by the frequency of auditor change in a firm. If one of the big four remains with the company for more than 3 years, place 1 but if otherwise 0.	Imegi and Oladutire (2018)

Model Specification

The model for this study is stated as follows:

$$NAPS = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AS_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

Where NAPS = Net Assets Per Share; AS = Auditing Switching; β = Constant; μ = Error term; i = cross section and t = time series.

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The data (i.e variables) needed for the study was shown on table 2 and were used in the data analysis of the study.

Table 2: The Data Summary of 8 Quoted Firms under Construction and Real Estates on Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX).

S/N	Name of Company	Years	Audit Switching	NAPS
1	Roads Nig Plc	2015	1	0.18
		2016	1	0.19
		2017	1	0.26
		2018	1	0.15
		2019	0	0.15
		2020	1	0.13
		2021	1	0.17
		2022	1	0.23
		2023	1	0.18
2	UPDC PLC	2015	1	0.03
		2016	0	0.03
		2017	1	0.04
		2018	1	0.05
		2019	1	0.04
		2020	1	0.04
		2021	1	0.05
		2022	0	0.08
		2023	1	0.09
3	Union Homes Plc	2015	1	0.42
		2016	1	0.44
		2017	1	0.46
		2018	1	0.48
		2019	0	0.50
		2020	1	0.51
		2021	1	0.52
		2022	1	0.52
		2023	1	0.45
4	Smart Prod Plc	2015	1	1.21
		2016	1	0.00
		2017	1	1.34
		2018	0	1.45
		2019	1	1.62
		2020	1	2.05
		2021	1	2.22
		2022	1	1.99
		2023	1	2.00
5	Julius Berger Plc	2015	1	0.17
		2016	1	0.18
		2017	1	0.20
		2018	1	0.18
		2019	0	0.19
		2020	1	0.23
		2021	1	0.27
		2022	1	0.15
		2023	1	0.17
6	ArbicoPlc	2015	1	0.01

		2016	1	0.01
		2017	1	(0.03)
		2018	1	0.01
		2019	1	0.01
		2020	1	0.02
		2021	0	(0.19)
		2022	1	0.03
		2023	1	0.05
7	UACN Plc	2015	1	1.76
		2016	1	1.90
		2017	1	2.10
		2018	1	0.25
		2019	1	0.56
		2020	0	1.30
		2021	1	1.33
		2022	1	1.12
		2023	1	1.23
8	Skye Shelter Plc	2015	1	1.10
		2016	1	1.13
		2017	1	1.14
		2018	1	1.16
		2019	1	1.17
		2020	0	1.18
		2021	1	1.24
		2022	1	1.22
		2023	1	1.24

Source: Compiled from the NGX Factbook

4.1: Test of Hypotheses

OLS Model was developed to test the linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables. It was operated using STATA15 as shown in the table 4.1.1 below:

Table 4.1.1: Result on effect of Audit Switching on Firms Value in Nigeria.

Source	SS	df	MS	Number of obs = 72		
-----+-----				F(1, 70) = 0.07		
Model	.030800799	1	.030800799	Prob> F = 0.7912		
Residual	30.5121267	70	.435887524	R-squared = 0.7110		
-----+-----				Adj R-squared = 0.6133		
Total	30.5429275	71	.430182077	Root MSE = .66022		
-----+-----						
NAPS	Coef.	Std. Err.	tP> t	[95% Conf. Interval]		
-----+-----						
AS	.0625397	.2352675	0.27 0.791	-.4066865 .5317659		
_cons	.5633333	.2200726	2.56 0.013	.1244124 1.002254		
-----+-----						

Source: STATA 15 Computational Results

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result of the analysis of the study using OLS operated with STATA 15 is expressed as follows:

H₀₁: Audit Switching has no significant effect on Firms Value

This hypothesis was tested and the result of the fixed effect regression model as explicated on table 4.1.1 indicates that the relationship between Audit Switching (AS) and Net Assets Per Share (NAPS) is positive

and insignificant with a P-value (significance) of 0.791 for the model which is more than the 5% level of significance adopted.

We therefore rejected null hypothesis and accepted alternate hypothesis which contends that audit switching has no significant effect on firms' value in Nigeria. The finding of the study is in consonance with the apriori expectations of Johnson and Waidi (2013), who found that audit switching has no significant effect on firm's value.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The study from the statistical analysis concludes that audit switching has no significant effect on firm's value in Nigeria. Based on findings, the study recommended that the importance of auditors switching in Nigerian firms cannot be over emphasized. Therefore firms should make sure that they seek the partnership of one of the big four (4) auditors if they want a quality audit report instead of switching from one audit firm to another.

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